

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Sixteen

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

The Steinsaltz Tehellim

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 16:0 A Mikhtam of David.</p>	<p>Psalm 16:1 מִכְתָּם לְדָוִד שְׁמִרְנִי</p>
<p>Psa. 16:1 Preserve me, O God, for I take refuge in You.</p>	<p>אֵל כִּי־חָסִיתִי בְּךָ : ² אֲמַרְתָּ</p>
<p>² I said to the LORD, “You are my Lord;</p>	<p>לִיהוָה אֲדַגֵּן אֶתְּהָ טוֹבָתִי בְּלִי־</p>
<p>I have no good besides You.”</p>	<p>עָלַיךָ : ³ לְקָרוֹשִׁים אֲשֶׁר־</p>
<p>³ As for the saints who are in the Earth,</p>	<p>בְּאֶרֶץ הַמָּוֶה וְאֲדִירָי כָּל־חֶפְצָי־</p>
<p>They are the majestic ones in whom is all my delight.</p>	<p>בָּם : ⁴ יִרְבּוּ עֲצָבוֹתָם אַחַר</p>
<p>⁴ The sorrows of those who have bartered for another <i>god</i> will be multiplied;</p>	<p>לְמַתָּרוֹ בְּלִי־אֲסִיף נִסְכֵי־הֵם מִדָּם</p>
<p>I shall not pour out their drink offerings of blood,</p>	<p>וְבִל־אֲשָׂא אֶת־שְׁמוֹתָם עַל־</p>
<p>Nor will I take their names upon my lips.</p>	<p>שִׁפְתָי : ⁵ יְהוָה מִנְת־חֶלְקִי</p>
<p>Psa. 16:5 The LORD is the portion of my inheritance and my cup;</p>	<p>וְכוֹסֵי אֶתְּהָ תוֹמִיךָ גּוֹרְלִי : ⁶</p>
<p>You support my lot.</p>	<p>חֲבָלִים נִפְלוּ־לִי בְּנַעֲמִים אַף־</p>
<p>⁶ The lines have fallen to me in pleasant places;</p>	<p>נִחַלְתָּ שִׁפְרָה עָלַי : ⁷ אֲבָרֶךָ</p>
<p>Indeed, my heritage is beautiful to me.</p>	<p>אֶת־יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר יַעֲצֵנִי אַף־</p>
<p>Psa. 16:7 I will bless the LORD who has counseled me;</p>	<p>לִילֹוֹת יִסְרוּנִי כְּלִי־חַיִּי : ⁸ שְׁוִיתִי</p>
<p>Indeed, my mind instructs me in the night.</p>	<p>יְהוָה לְנִגְנְדֵי תָמִיד כִּי מִי־מִינִי</p>
<p>⁸ I have set the LORD continually before me;</p>	<p>בְּלִי־אֲמוּט : ⁹ לָכֵן אֲשַׁמַּח לְבִי</p>
<p>Because He is at my right hand, I will not be shaken.</p>	<p>וַיִּגַּל כְּבוֹדֵי אַף־בְּשָׁרִי יִשְׁכַּן</p>
	<p>לְבַטָּח : ¹⁰ כִּי אֵל־תַּעֲזֹב נִפְשִׁי</p>
	<p>לְשֹׂאוֹל לֹא־תִתֵּן תְּסִידֶךָ</p>
	<p>לְרֹאוֹת שְׁתַּת : ¹¹ תּוֹדִיעֵנִי אֶרֶח</p>

<p>⁹ Therefore my heart is glad and my glory rejoices; My flesh also will dwell securely.</p> <p>¹⁰ For You will not abandon my soul to Sheol; Nor will You allow Your Holy One to undergo decay.</p> <p>¹¹ You will make known to me the path of life; In Your presence is fullness of joy; In Your right hand there are pleasures forever.</p>	<p>תָּנִים שִׁבַּע שְׂמֹחֹת אֶת־פָּנֶיךָ נְעֻמֹת בְּיַמִּינְךָ נִצַּחַת :</p>
---	--

Targum

Psa. 16:1 An honest inscription of David. Protect me, O God, because I have hoped in your word. ² You have spoken – you, my soul – in the presence of the LORD. You are my God, truly my goodness is not present without you. ³ To the holy ones that are in the land they have declared the might of my power from the beginning; and as for those proud of their good deeds, my good will is for them. ⁴ But the wicked multiply their idols; afterwards they hurry to make their sacrifices. I will not receive favorably their libations or the blood of their sacrifices, nor will I mention their name with my lips. ⁵ The LORD is the portion of my cup and my share; you will support my lot. ⁶ The lots have fallen pleasantly for me; indeed, a beautiful inheritance is mine. ⁷ I will bless the LORD, who has counseled me; even at night my mind disciplines me. ⁸ I have placed the LORD before me always, for his presence rests on me; I shall not be shaken. ⁹ Therefore, my heart is glad, and my glory rejoices; besides, my flesh shall dwell in security. ¹⁰ For you will not abandon my soul to Sheol, you will not hand over your innocent one to see corruption. ¹¹ You will tell me the way of life; abundance of joy is in the presence of your face; pleasant things are at your right hand forever.

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
A Mikhtam of David.	מִכְתָּם לְדָוִד

Verse Analysis

מִכְתָּם לְדָוִד (meektam leDavid) – This phrase is translated as “a mikhtam of David” in the NASB 1995 Bible. The lexicon entry is:

“מִכְתָּם (*miktām*) **miktam**. A technical term that appears in Psalm titles. Meaning unknown.

This term is used in six Psalm titles, always linked with לְדָוִד “of” or “belonging to David” (**Ps 16** and Ps 56–59). All six are psalms of lament and four of the headings have historical references to David’s struggles with the Philistines (56), Saul (57, 59) and the Arameans (60). If it comes from a root “to cover” (cf. Akkadian *katāmu*). מִכְתָּם could mean a “song of covering” or “atonement.” Another view understands the term to mean an “engraving,” such as an inscription on a stone slab, perhaps with gold letters (כְּתָם = gold).”

The Targum says “an honest inscription” of David for the superscript. Rabbi Steinsaltz uses the translation “an instruction by David.”

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A psalm of thanksgiving by David

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Psa. 16:1 Preserve me, O God, for I take refuge in You	שְׁמֵרֵנִי אֱלֹהִים כִּי־תִסְתֵּר בְּךָ ²

Verse Analysis

שְׁמֵרֵנִי אֱלֹהִים (shameranee el) this phrase can be translated as either “preserve me” or “keep me.” It refers to David’s mistake that he believed that the LORD was so far away from the Earth that He would not see what was happening on Earth. Through the Bathsheba incident, David realized the mistake that he had made that the LORD was aware of his sin. After his repentance, he asked the LORD to protect him.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Hold me close to you, LORD, by allowing me to feel the presence of your Shekinah with me all the days of my life.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
2 I said to the LORD, “You are my Lord; I have no good besides You.”	אָמַרְתָּ לַיהוָה אֱלֹהֵי אֶתְהָא טוֹבָתִי בַל-עֲלִיךָ

Verse Analysis

אָמַרְתָּ (amart) – this word can be translated as “I said.” However, the term is implying much more. The term is in a feminine form of address and conveys that the person thus spoken to is weak.

David writes this Psalm as a reminder of how he should act through the rest of his life. He wanted the Shekinah to be with him and be realized that the LORD sees everything. There is no place on Earth to hide from divine justice.

טוֹבָתִי (tovatee) – can be translated as “good.” It means good earthly happiness and welfare.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

I said to the LORD that all my earthly goodness and welfare comes from you.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ As for the saints who are in the Earth, They are the majestic ones in whom is all my delight.</p>	<p>לְקַדְוֹשִׁים אֲשֶׁר-בְּאֶרֶץ הַמָּה וְאֵדִיָּי כָּל-תְּפִצֵּי-בָם :</p>

Verse Analysis

לְקַדְוֹשִׁים (leek'dosheem) – this word refers to super-terrestrial beings who are close to the LORD. It is not completely clear in the Bible who these beings are. The Watchers described in Genesis six and in the Book of the Watchers from 1 Enoch could be classified as super-terrestrial beings close to the LORD. They were angels who asked the LORD to come to the Earth and live among humans. The NASB 1995 translation is “saints who are in the earth.” The Watchers would be disqualified from being these creatures. They were condemned to live on Earth, but they believed that they brought evil and despair to the world. The beings that David was speaking of is not known.

David was asking for these creatures to help him to fulfill all of his desires.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Through the holy super-terrestrial beings who are a part of the Earth, they will fulfill all my desires.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ The sorrows of those who have bartered for another <i>god</i> will be multiplied;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I shall not pour out their drink offerings of blood,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Nor will I take their names upon my lips.</p>	<p>יְרַבּוּ עֲצָבוֹתָם אֲחֵר מִתְּרוּ 4 :</p> <p>בַּל־אֶסְיֹךְ נִסְפִיָּהֶם מִדָּם וְבַל־</p> <p>אֶשָּׂא אֶת־שְׁמוֹתָם עַל־שִׁפְתָּי :</p>

Verse Analysis

The tie of marriage illustrates the pure relationship between the LORD and humans. Each partner seeks an alliance with the other. Some people create an alliance with idols and false gods. The person who places himself/herself under the rule of the LORD will not suffer the pain that a person does who relies on idols and false gods.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

About the sufferings of people who ally themselves to an idol, a false god; I will not pour out their drink offerings of blood. Nor will I speak their names.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Psa. 16:5 The LORD is the portion of my inheritance and my cup; You support my lot.	5 יְהוָה מְנַת-חֶלְקִי וְכוּסִי אֵתָהּ תוֹמֵךְ גּוֹרְלִי :

Verse Analysis

David acknowledges that his inheritance, that is, the goodness of his life on Earth, is from the LORD. He recognizes this fact. David also acknowledges that his inheritance may make him lower than his lowest subject. That was all right because David fully surrendered to the divine will.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD is the portion of my inheritance that He gives to me. I accept whatever is given to me.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁶ The lines have fallen to me in pleasant places; Indeed, my heritage is beautiful to me.</p>	<p>חֲבֵלִים נָפְלוּ-לִי בְּנֵעִמִּים אֶרֶץ- נִחְלָת שְׂפָרָה עָלַי :</p>

Verse Analysis

“The lines” mean the luck that has come to David, i.e., winning a lottery. The inheritance David received was also pleasing and beautiful.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The luck that has fallen upon me is pleasant. My inheritance is also beautiful.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 16:7 I will bless the LORD who has counseled me; Indeed, my mind instructs me in the night.</p>	<p>אֲבָרֵךְ אֶת־יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר יְעֲצָנִי אֶךְ־לַיְלֹת יִסְרוּנִי כְּלַיְוֹתַי :</p>

Verse Analysis

David says that he blessed the LORD who prevented him from using the wrong path through life. David regrets the wrong paths that he took in his life.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

I will bless the LORD who has given me instruction to keep me on the right path and for the nights in which my Nefesh's (flesh) desires to try to control me.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁸I have set the LORD continually before me; Because He is at my right hand, I will not be shaken.</p>	<p>שׁוֹיִתִּי יְהוָה לְנֶגְדִי תָמִיד כִּי 8 כִּי מִיָּמֵי בֶל-אָמוֹט :</p>

Verse Analysis

David acknowledges his understanding that nothing on Earth is so small or insignificant that the LORD would simply ignore it.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD is continually with me and seeing what I am doing. I will not be frightened that He is always at my right hand.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁹ Therefore my heart is glad and my glory rejoices; My flesh also will dwell securely.</p>	<p>לִכְנֹן אֶשְׂמַח לְבַי וַיִּגַּלֵּן⁹ : כְּבוֹדִי אֶף-בְּשָׂרִי יִשְׁכֵּן לְבֶטֶחַ :</p>

Verse Analysis

Again David acknowledges that all good comes from the LORD. A person can never obtain true happiness without having the LORD as a part of their lives.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Therefore my heart is glad when my glory rejoices. My Nefesh dwells in security.

Verse Ten

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁰ For You will not abandon my soul to Sheol; Nor will You allow Your Holy One to undergo decay.</p>	<p>כִּי לֹא־תַעֲזֹב נַפְשִׁי ¹⁰ : לְשָׂאוֹל לֹא־תִתֵּן חֲסִידְךָ לְרָאוֹת שְׁחַת :</p>

Verse Analysis

This verse is interesting because it conveys an understanding of the Hellenistic idea of separating body and spirit. In the Near East, the idea of the spirit and body separating at death did not come until the Greek invasion. However, it appears to have been known in David's day. Alternatively, perhaps it was not known, and this Psalm was composed at a much later time and attributed to David.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You, LORD, will not abandon my Spirit to the depths of Sheol, nor will you allow your servant to undergo destruction.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹¹ You will make known to me the path of life; In Your presence is fullness of joy; In Your right hand there are pleasures forever.</p>	<p>¹¹ : הוֹדִיעֵנִי אֶרְחַב תַּיִם שְׂבַע שְׂמֵחֹת אֶת־פְּנֵיךָ נְעֻמֹת בְּיָמֶיךָ נֶצַח :</p>

Verse Analysis

The path that the LORD placed David upon was filled with nothing but life.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You will make my path known as the path of life. In your presence is the fullness of all good things. In your right hand are pleasures forever.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A psalm of thanksgiving by David

Hold me close to you, LORD, by allowing me to feel the presence of your Shekinah with me all the days of my life.

I said to the LORD that all my earthly goodness and welfare comes from you.

Through the holy super-terrestrial beings who are a part of the Earth, they will fulfill all my desires.

About the sufferings of people who ally themselves to an idol, a false god; I will not pour out their drink offerings of blood. Nor will I speak their names.

The LORD is the portion of my inheritance that He gives to me. I accept whatever is given to me.

The luck that has fallen upon me is pleasant. My inheritance is also beautiful.

I will bless the LORD who has given me instruction to keep me on the right path and for the nights in which my Nefesh's (flesh) desires to try to control me.

The LORD is continually with me and seeing what I am doing. I will not be frightened that He is always at my right hand.

Therefore my heart is glad when my glory rejoices. My Nefesh dwells in security.

You, LORD, will not abandon my Spirit to the depths of Sheol, nor will you allow your servant to undergo destruction.

You will make my path known as the path of life. In your presence is the fullness of all good things. In your right hand are pleasures forever

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

